

Implications of Work-Life Balance on Career Development in Health Sector at Khairpur Mir's

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Abstract

An implication of work-life balance on career development in health sector at Khairpur Mir's is ascertained in this study. There were 30 participants from various public sector health organizations, from which 14 respondents were observed via interviews and 16 people took active part in questionnaire survey. Interview & questionnaire survey was based on structured style having 15 items that measured the level of work-life balance and its impact on certain defined variables. Whereas work-life balance is independent variable and career development is dependent variable. Impact of work-life on career development is observed via five variables of work-life, named as: Work, Pay, Job security, Family life & entertainment. Cronbach's alpha is obtained and data is processed in Nvivo 10 software to get results. Three queries are run in Nvivo 10 namely: Text search query, word frequency query & matrix coding query, to get the results and to know the relation of variables to one another. Work-life with its variables has the effective relation with career development. It is observed in the results that there is optimistic relation among variables taken. This research is a qualitative study and is taken in health sector at Khairpur Mir's.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Work itself, Pay, Job Security, Family Life, Entertainment & Career Development.

Introduction

There goes a saying that "Never gets so busy in living that you forget to make life". It was a time when the limits between work and life were fairly clear in each and every sectors of society. Now days, however, work is likely to assault our personal life and maintaining work-life balance is not an effortless task. Until and unless work-life balance is not out of reach. To do overwork also takes its charge on employee satisfaction and creativity. Bruce Van Horn, CEO of Yogaforbusiness.com writes about work-life that, "We need to be human beings in organization, not human doers". No doubt, Work is such a large part of our life that it can seem easier to forgot the other areas such as recreation, mysticism and family, to name just a few. But it's very much important that one should find enough time to enjoy all different aspects of life, otherwise you can burn out.

This research study aims to provide the implications of work-Life balance on career development in health sector at Khairpur Mir's. When work life and personal life are out of balance, stress level is likely to soar. This research study focus on such issues which really creates disturbance in making balance between work and life in health sector and influence the career development of an employee in organization. According to Diane Domeyer; a philosopher, organizations today can't ignore the issue of work-life balance. Providing employee flexibility to address personal commitments, without compromising the needs of business, can make a difference between a

good working environment and great one. It is really true that life is all about balance taking the good with bad.

According to research studies by the national institute of occupational health, American businesses lose more than \$300 billion a year due to absenteeism, employee turnover and career development and workers' compensation benefits directly resulting from overwork. Simply it is obvious that Work-life balance is a concept including proper prioritizing between works. Work means not only work but made up of career and ambition and lifestyle with health, pleasure, leisure, family and spiritual development. Also this issue of work-life balance includes lifestyle calm balance and lifestyle choices to have no any negative impact of work.

Life is all about balance, too much and too little can kill. Simply the best way to balance life is by setting your boundaries in learning to say enough. This issue of work-life is really a best way to restore harmony and reduce stress. It is general phenomenon; we work because we have to. People usually understand the world of work as it relates to making money. However, it is not. Hillary Rodham Clinton once said "Our lives are a mixture of different roles. Most of us are doing the best we can to find whatever the right balance is for me, that balance is family, work, and service"

Literature Review

Researcher in this article shares experience about the work-life practices in an organization. How an organization should focus on the policies which can

manage the balance between work and family life in a job environment. Author in his this qualitative research aims to explore policies associated with flexi time. The human resource practitioner must try to manage those policies in organization which cannot produce any issue against work-life. These both the issues are very serious for organization to be focused, especially nowadays employees are very conscious in maintaining their work and life in a balanced form. According to author, there should flexi time policies to face the challenges of work-life issues. (Downes, et al., 2011)

This research aims to support the work-life balance in an organization. Here the researcher shows his positive sign towards work-life balance because now the trend has been changed, and one should not neglect his focus on the individual rights. There is also positive impact of work-life balance is shown with indirect relation with organization growth. Both parties, organization as well employee have been well aware about the possible remuneration of work-life balance. It has been a serious and really a key factor for employee satisfaction, no doubt employee satisfaction is directly linked with job satisfaction. This issue of work-life balance can also solve many other problems in organization, such as high turnover, poor job performance, and absenteeism. (Morgan, 2009)

The focus of this research is on the different issues of employees and his behavior towards work-life balance that how an employee respond the work-life balance issue in organization. According to author, one of research in past years has shown that 38 % of employees are keen interested in work-life issues and that is the basic reason, that employee turnover to another organization to search for better work-life balance policies. Author believes that work-life balance practices can decrease turnover and increase its growth. It would be beneficial for organization development. Now a day's employer on the stage of recruiting employee must focus on the work-life balance as time is changed and organization trends have also been changed. (Dex., et al., 2004)

Work and life are the main focus of today's time. As each and every organization feels a need to implement such policies that should be beneficial in a combined form. One policy effect should be multi-dimensional. Author here focus on the survey with different organizations and their defensive strategies towards work-life balance. Human resource management should determine their success associated with work-life balance. Other issues are also much important but if employee would feel not comfortable with his work,

how would he comfort organization with his efforts? Policies should be associated with flexi time. Neither it may neglect organization nor may it impact employee work-life. (G.F, et al., 2005)

Research shows the true picture of each and every thing, problem may what be, but research has opened the doors of solution for every problem. Work-life is also a key problem for some of the organization and also headache for others. The author aims to explain certain impact of international study of workplace sanity. Author not from his side but with the different truths of history makes a mystery for organization. Organization who believes work life as a minor issue, it is not good for them. Also organization who takes it impossible, it is also bad. There should be balance in maintaining work and life, because international survey also supports this view that one should understand the present and past trends. Also researcher discusses flexi time practices that organization should apply in its surroundings. (Willig, 2008)

This research has been given its focus on work-like balance in whole south East Asia; researcher main focus is on the country of India. This study has used certain case studies with verbal interviews which are based on real work-life as India is a big populated country. In this paper, some new interference are focused with work and family life, which are of gender impartiality, elasticity, pressure diminution, fitness awareness and baby care. Work-life balance is a basic tool towards these issues. No doubt here work and life is being focus in contradiction with socio economic development in India region, but it can be in any other region of the world. Work-life balance is equal important for male and female employee as females are also part of society and are highly engaged in workforce in all over the world. HR should play vital role in solving such problems. (Rajadhyaksha, 2012)

Researcher in this article discuss several fact of real life associated with work and life. Author has focused on the different issues of generation that past years study has shown that increase in work force in both the members of family, individuals, household and parents. So an organization should give view to these factors that an employee should balance in all things that may be job performance or family liability.

If this gap of balance in certain variables of work-life be filled with proper policies and its implementation in organization, so there will be suitable working conditions for both employer and employee. Nation which is developed has made hubs to keep obedience in range of socio economic norms, to face psychological

issues, managerial manners, work finances, business associations and organizational demographics. These issues of WLB should be seriously treated. (Neal, et al., 2007)

This research paper is a literature review based paper; it focuses on the work-life interventions associated with work-stress, work-life clash, career orientation, turnover and malingering. This study reviews the interrelations of these factors as a basic tool to measure the importance work-life for employer as well for employee. Work-life balance in organization is as much as job satisfaction is being focused by organization, especially in various sections, it is a dominant factor among all to be cared. Here in this paper author from different sources has taken different variables mentioned above and then combining the importance and balance between those and work-life. Another thing which is being focused in this paper, it is communication gap associated with work and life in between employee and employer. Normally work-life issues are concerned with employee but it becomes headache for organization, no doubt organizations have to maintain this situation in order to overcome this. (Singh, 2013)

Author in this study gives view that organization are very much interested in adopting change now a day's. By the changing time several factors has been raised for organization concerned. Among those work-life is one of the major issues in work place sanity to be focused and handled with care. There should be serious consideration by HR towards work-life. As society is moving ahead, it had given birth to too many other things which socially and economically associated work-life norms. According to author organization would address work-life issue as a competitive advantage in market place and find out various work-life balances challenging situation to propose a win-win answer. Here author also suggests increasing employee morale. An Organization can get success when it maintains the rapidity with workplace development. (Lockwood, 2003)

This research study suggests some new meaning and concepts of work-life balance. According to author, work and life issues are concerned with different things to various groups of people according to their thinking and nature. Employer takes work-life as a culture of organization and takes steps to maintain its culture in an appropriate way, while employee should feel his responsibility to direct himself in a way that he should perform his work and life liability properly. Author also speaks about the American organizations that these believes work-life as an ethical issue and must remain unharmed. Both issues, personnel as well family life

should be go together. There was a survey taken in America region in 2001 by Radcliff public policy center, so it showed that males ratio were 82% and females ratio were 85 %, their ages were placed from 20 to 40, they keep their family at the peak of work-life balance. Organization should go towards adopting flexi time policies to satisfy their employees in proper way. It would be beneficial for both employer & employee. (Swift, Jan, 2003)

Theoretical Framework

The aim we for this research study is to know the impact of work-life balance on career development and employee performance mediated by Work-Life Balance in a health sector. The relationship between dependent variable and independent variables is shown in this paper. The objective of the research is to examine the work-life balance and its impact on career development. Also the impact of work-life issues on employee job performance is analyzed in this study.

The independent variable is one, which influences the dependent variable in an optimistic or pessimistic way. The independent variable of the study is work-life balance. Means issues associated with work and life intervention, simply it can be said that life to work and work to life intervention. The sub variables of work-life are observed here, these are, work, Pay, Job Security, and Family Life & Entertainment. These issues focus is on the working conditions of work itself, work seems to put light on the stress associated with life and work independence is analyzed. The model is also constructed given below. Now this study is very clear to show the impact of independent variable having its sub variables and there affect on the dependent variable.

Work itself is a general activity performed by every individual involving mental or physical effort done in order to achieve a result. It can also be said a task or tasks to be undertaken. So here in this study its affect is being analyzed on the performance. Whereas work associated with stress is a state of mental or emotional strain or tension resulting from adverse or demanding circumstances. While some workplace stress is normal, excessive stress can interfere with your productivity and impact your physical and emotional health. Employee ability to deal with it can mean the difference between success and failure. Job autonomy is simply the right of employee or condition of self-government. This paper suggests the certain facts of these issues concerned with job performance in order to address common issues caused now days in every organization.

The dependent variable is one of most essential part on every research study. Dependent variables are those which are being influenced by the independent, may be positively or negatively. Furthermore the difference in dependent variable is clarified by the difference of independent variable. Here in this study employee job satisfaction and job performance are the dependent variables which are being influenced by the independent variables. Here is simple model is structured in order to give representation of work-life and employee retention.

Research Objectives

This research paper has the following research objectives:

- To examine the Work-life balance issues associated career development
- To analyze the factors that impacts the Work-life
- To focus on the basic relations of work & life that leads to poor job performance
- To obtain essentials measures for work-life balance & career development

Research Problem

This research study aims to observe the impact factors of work-life balance on career development in health sector at Khairpur Mir's and to inspect the different variables that impact the work-life of employees of health sector, where as a few essential variables of work and life are used in this research study to assess their connection associated with job career development. The key question conduct this study is:

“What are the work and life influence over career development of employees that creates disturbance in between work-balance”?

Research Hypotheses

- Work-life with work itself, pay, job security, family life, & entertainment are different terms treated in different way with different measures.
- Work, pay and job security are associated with working conditions and have direct influence on satisfaction towards career development.

- Family and entertainment are linked with life of employee which also direct shed effect on satisfaction towards career development of employee.
- Work, Life and Employee interest towards the job are key factors that put impact on employee decisions regarding job satisfaction and performance.

Methodology

This is a qualitative research study to know and analyze the implications of work-life balance on career development in health sector organization. To get the better understandings to facts that are highly linked with work and life issues. Most of data of this paper is gathered and observed via primary sources.

• Research Sampling

In this study participants are from health sector organizations having MBBS, FPCS & MCPS qualification, from Khairpur Mir's, who took active part by giving their time for interview and survey. Sample size is based on 30 people, 14 for interview and 16 for survey.

• Research Method

The data being used in this paper is got from primary & secondary sources. Knowledge about various facts is observed by getting interview from many people and questionnaire survey to know the implications of work-life balance. The purpose of this paper is to identify the factors that are correlated to work and life and causes effect on career development of employee.

Structured interview was exercised to get the observation and questionnaire was used having lingered scales. 15 items questionnaire was made by approval of supervisor. Data was processed via Nvivo 10 to get results. Three queries were run namely: text search query, word frequency query and matrix coding query. Certain outcomes are observed by these queries and are showed in appendix section. This research paper is concerned with the implications of work-life balance on career development of health sector at Khairpur Mir's.

Research Model

Research model showing Work-Life Balance influencing career development where as career development is dependent variable & Work-life Balance variables are independent variables.

Results & Discussion

❖ **Table 1 Work-Life Variables Coverage**

Parent Node with its Child Nodes						
Work-Life Balance	Training Opportunities	Pay/Salary	Work Place	Job Security	Working Hours	Career Development
0.96	0.05	0.03	0.08	0.05	0.08	0.08

This above mentioned table shows the variables outputs of data interpreted by Nvivo 10 as described earlier. It was gained by making parent nodes and Childs and their comparison with the data we obtained via interview and questionnaire survey. There is a positive value defined in

the table that surely means that there is good coverage of variables upon each other. It also shows that there is good and positive relation. These parent and child nodes are made viewing the research work and responses.

❖ **Table 2 Work Variables Coverage**

Parent Node with its Child Nodes			
Work	Work Itself	Pay/ Salary	Job Security
0.96	0.75	0.77	0.87

This table also represents variables coverage, but the variables defined in this are not similar to that one in first table also their coverage is different. Here the values show that there is much positive and strong

relation among variables. We can say that work has direct implications over life and career development.

❖ **Table 3 Family Life Variables Coverage**

Parent Node with its Child Nodes		
Family Life	Entertainment	Employee Personal Life
0.96	0.875	0.876

Here in this table family life with its child nodes are shown. The results are much more effective and build strong relation. Here the values are nearly related to each other. Work-life balance surely impacts the family life

and employee life is being disturbs if it would not be handled with care. The results are obtained by using qualitative software Nvivo 10.

❖ **Table 4 variables Coverage**

Parent Node with its Child Nodes		
Career Development	Growth	Employee Interest
0.96	0.875	0.879

This table denotes the variables associated with career development and shows its relation with job growth and employee interest towards work and life. Also its impact on career development because these all above

Conclusion

It is observed from this research study that work-life is linked to each other and have direct impact on career development. Variables that were studied in this paper have better coverage upon career development in health sector. We can say that there is good and positive relation between all variables. Health sector at Khairpur Mir's can be influenced if the work-life balance is not handled with care. A good work-life balance is very important in our life. Working is necessary and hardworking is surely not bad but we need to find the right balance to keep our system healthy. No doubt setting healthy boundaries is essential for a healthy work-life balance.

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mentioned tables is linked with work-life balance issues and career development. Here is this table again values are much more effective and shows good sign of coverage.

Limitations & Future directions

This research paper is property of our team & should not get copied accordingly. Researchers can use this paper as a guide paper to get knowledge about this. This study is conducted to know the implications of work-life balance on career development. This study is concerned with health sector at Khairpur Mir's. There are also many variables of work-life balance that are not studied in this paper and also a health sector varies by location. Here we have focused only five variables that are specific, but other variables should be focused in order to have more knowledge regarding work-life balance

Figure-3

Figure-4

Figure-5

Figure 6

Figure 7

